

MICROSTRUCTURAL ASPECTS ON FRACTURE AND FATIGUE OF SHORT FIBER COMPOSITES WITH HIGH TEMPERATURE RESISTANT THERMOPLASTIC MATRICES

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ABSTRACT

Both the fracture and fatigue behavior of high temperature resistant thermoplastic plaques with discontinuous fiber reinforcement are strongly affected by the microstructural details. The latter, induced by injection molding processing of the plaques, can be summarized in a reinforcing effectiveness parameter, R . This parameter treats a short fiber reinforced injection-molded composite as a laminate, in the layers of which the fibers show different orientations and in addition, various aspect ratios and aspect ratio distributions. The relative change in the fracture toughness can be predicted by the microstructural efficiency concept (M), the constituents of which are R , the matrix stress conditon factor (a) and the energy absorption ratio (n). Due to analogies between static fracture and fatigue crack growth results this concept can also be used for a systematic understanding of the dependancy of the latter on microstructural variations.

KEY WORDS: Failure mechanism; Fatigue; Fracture; Injection-molding; Short fiber composite

1. INTRODUCTION

Injection-molded, short glass (GF) and carbon fiber (CF) reinforced composites with temperature resistant thermoplastic matrices such as polyetheretherketone (PEEK), polyphenylenesulfide (PPS) and polyethernitrile (PEN) are potential candidates for being used in technical domains, so far occupied by metallic and ceramic materials. Short fiber reinforcements provide high stiffness, strength and dimensional stability to these matrices rendering them suitable for different applications in automotive, transportation and electric or electronic fields. These applications, on the other hand, require that these materials also possess high resistance against fatigue, dynamic (impact) and static fracture (tensile mode). In the present paper it is outlined how the fracture and fatigue performance of composites with discontinuous fiber reinforcement can be correlated with their microstructural

details, e.g. fiber orientation, layer structure etc. as developed during the injection molding process.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials Film-gated injection-molded plaques of 3-4 mm thickness with GF and CF reinforcement in the range of 10 to 30 wt.% were supplied by the LNP Engineering Plastics, Malvern, PA, USA (PPS composites based on a Ryton grade of Phillips Petroleum, Bartlesville, OK, USA), by ICI Ltd, Wilton, UK (Victrex PEEK 450 G based composites) and by Idemitsu Kosan Co, Chiba, Japan (PEN ID 300 based composites). Their characterization - with the only exception of PEN-composites - can be found in references [1-3].

2.2 Testing Compact tension (CT) specimens were cut from the injection molded plaques and notched either parallel or perpendicular to the mold filling direction (MFD). Static fracture tests were performed on a Zwick 1445 type tensile machine at different temperatures and deformation rates. The fracture toughness (K_{IC}), was calculated according to the ASTM E 399 standard. Fatigue crack propagation (FCP) measurements were carried out in tensile-tensile mode ($R=0.2$) on a Schenck PSA 10 kN servohydraulic machine at ambient temperature using the same CT specimens and a sinusoidal wave function of 5 Hz frequency. Other necessary experimental details can be taken from our previous works (e.g. [1-4]).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure Development The molding-induced microstructure both of the unfilled matrices and the short fiber reinforced grades can be properly described by the flow model of Tadmor [5] and Rose [6]. This model considers the shear and elongational flow field evoked during the cavity filling process. The molding-induced matrix morphology of these high melting temperature plastics of polycondensation type and with a T_g far beyond the mold temperature is a rather simple one composed of skin and core layers [1,2,4]. Although, it was suggested [4] that this skin-core structure affect the fracture and especially the fatigue performance quite considerably these aspects do not belong to the scope of this contribution. The reinforcing fibers, on the other hand, may adopt a rather complex alignment due to the dominating flow field and thus several layers with different planar fiber orientation can be distinguished across the specimen thickness. Due to the rather low molecular mass of the virgin polymers the fiber structuring can well be approximated by a 3-ply laminate model composed of one central (C) and two surface (S) layers. In these layers the mean fiber orientation can be characterized by different ways, from which in our case a modified Hermans type was preferred (Figure 1). It has been also shown that the fiber layering and orientation depend on the fiber volume fraction (V_f), fiber aspect ratio (l/d) and - provided that the diameter of the fiber is the same - on the fiber length distribution (l_w/l_N - where subscripts W and N relate to the weight and number

average). The microstructure of the short fiber reinforced composites in respect with the loading direction can be characterized by the reinforcing effectiveness parameter (R) [8-9]:

$$R = \left(\frac{2S}{B} \cdot f_{p,eff,S} + \frac{C}{B} \cdot f_{p,eff,C} \right) \cdot V_f \cdot \left(\frac{1}{d} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1_w} \right) \quad (1)$$

where B is the specimen thickness and all other terms were defined before.

Fiber Orientation Factor

$$f_p = 2 \langle \cos^2 \varphi \rangle - 1$$

$$\langle \cos^2 \varphi \rangle = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n N_{(\varphi_i)} \cdot \cos^2 \varphi_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n N_{(\varphi_i)}}$$

Effective Fiber Orientation Factor

$$f_{p,eff} = \alpha [1 + \tanh(\beta \cdot f_p)]$$

$$\alpha = 0.5$$

$$1 < \beta < 5$$

FIGURE 1. Relation between fiber orientation and effective fiber orientation with respect of the loading direction

FIGURE 2. Evaluation of the factors "a" and "n" on the example of GF- and CF-reinforced PEN composites (Testing conditions: T=RT, v= 1 mm/min crosshead speed)

3.2 Fracture Toughness

The microstructural efficiency concept [8] seems to be a powerful tool to estimate the change in fracture toughness due to reinforcement. According to this concept the fracture toughness of the composite related to that of the matrix at a given testing condition linearly depends on R (cf. also Figure 2):

$$\frac{K_{c,c}}{K_{c,m}} = M = a + n \cdot R \quad (2)$$

where

$K_{c,c}$ and $K_{c,m}$ are the fracture toughness of the composite and matrix, respectively

"a" is the matrix stress condition factor

"n" is the energy absorption ratio

The relative improvement in the toughness of the composite is plotted against the reinforcing effectiveness (R) for the PPS, PEN and PEEK composites (Figure 3). Based on Figure 3 one can conclude that with increasing matrix toughness the energy absorption ratio (n) decreases. This statement is also valid when analogous effects of testing conditions (increasing temperature or decreasing deformation rate or frequency) are considered. The sign of "n" is positive in these materials indicating that the energy absorption by fiber-related failure events (fiber fracture, pull-out and fiber/matrix debonding) is higher than that of the matrix-related one. For GF-PEEK and GF-PEN $n \approx 0$ which means that the failure is practically matrix-dominated, i.e. incorporation of fibers does not cause any changes in failure manner due to the high matrix ductility.

FIGURE 3. Relative effectiveness in toughness improvement of the polymer matrices studied by fiber reinforcement (Testing conditions: $T=RT$, $v=1$ mm/min crosshead speed); Note: $K_{c,m}$ in $MPa \cdot m^{1/2}$ units.

The characteristic failure modes as a function of temperature and deformation rate (or frequency) are often summarized in failure maps [10-11]. Such a failure map (cf. Figure 4) gives instructions for example

- i- how the high toughness range of PEEK could be expanded (into higher temperatures by copolymerization, crosslinking; into higher deformation rates via toughening, increasing the molecular weight - as it can be suggested from the patent literature)
- ii- which are the basic fiber related failure events which have to be studied upon further material development (in the high toughness range pull-out processes are of basic importance)

In addition, mapping of fracture toughness or fracture energy as a function of the temperature- and frequency-dependant E-moduli (fracture maps) contains valuable informations fore design and constructions. For PEEK and PPS such fracture maps were constructed and published [1,2,11].

FIGURE 4. Failure map showing characteristic failure and fracture toughness values for the unfilled and GF-reinforced PEEK

3.3 Fatigue Crack Propagation (FCP)

Under cyclic loading conditions final failure of the short fiber reinforced composites is governed by fatigue crack propagation (FCP) instead of crack initiation process. This is due to the fact that an inherent notch in form of structural inhomogeneity is always present. The stable FCP range can be described by the well-known Paris-Erdogan power law [12]:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = A \cdot (\Delta K)^m \quad (3)$$

The effects of the microstructural constituents on the FCP run are summarized schematically in Figure 5 on the example of GF-

and CF-PEN composites. Since the upper bound of the validity of the Paris range is at about K_{cc} and the related failure events are also very similar at subcritical and critical loadings, between the fatigue and fracture test results several analogies are expected. Increasing R therefore should rise the resistance against fatigue crack growth in these materials, in agreement with the experimental results [3-4,11] (Figure 6).

FIGURE 5. Schematic of the effects of microstructural factors on the position of the FCP curves on the example of short fiber filled PEN-composites

Based on Figure 5 Equation 3 can be modified assuming that its constants are functions of M:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = \left(\frac{A}{M}\right) \cdot (\Delta K)^{m(M)} \quad (4)$$

$$\log\left(\frac{da}{dN}\right) = \log A - \log(a+n \cdot R) + m(M) \cdot \log(\Delta K) \quad (5)$$

Equation 5 simplifies further as $m(M)$ or $m(M) \cdot \log(\Delta K)$ can be treated as constants due to the moderate change in the exponential factor "m" with M. In such a case for the $\log(da/dn)$ vs $\log M$ data pairs a straight line can easily be fitted, which was shown for PEEK composites in fact [3]. It seems that the last assumption is the easier fulfilled the lower the energy absorption ratio (n) is, with other words, the higher the ductility of the matrix is. It should be noted here, that the latter estimation functions well provided that the valid Paris

range is broad enough.

FIGURE 6. ΔK ranges at selected da/dN values for the CF-PEN composites

4. CONCLUSIONS

Improvement in fracture toughness and fatigue crack propagation behavior achieved by fiber incorporation strongly depends on the matrix characteristics. This effect is the higher the lower the matrix toughness is. Both the fracture toughness and the fatigue crack propagation (FCP) rate can be correlated to the microstructure of the composites by means of the microstructural efficiency factor (M). Fractographic analysis revealed that the dominant failure events are practically the same - excluding the effects of crack tip heating - in both tests. This is a further argument for the reliability of this microstructural efficiency concept.

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7.BIOGRAPHY

József Karger-Kocsis, born in 1950, worked first in the Research Institute for the Plastics Industry in Budapest, Hungary. He received his Ph.D. from chemical engineering at the Moscow Institute for Fine Chemicals Technology in Moscow, 1983. Later he was employed by the Taurus Hungarian Rubber Works as chief engineer in a factory in Budapest. His D.Sc. received from the Hungarian Academy of Sciences in Budapest, 1990. After a 2 years research stay as Alexander von Humboldt fellow and an additional 2 years period as scientific coworker in the Composites Group of Prof.K.Friedrich at the Technical University Hamburg-Harburg, he has joined to the Institute for Composite Materials Ltd. at the University of Kaiserslautern as department head of the Materials Science Division.